

Purification of further GS loop mutants of ALK2 (ACVR1) and ACVR2 (type 2 receptor) to investigate necessary phosphorylation's for SMAD1 activation.

Constructs purified:

ACVR1Z-c108 (1I)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCSTSGSAGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARRMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

ACVR1Z-c113 (1I)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHACAAGSGSGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRY
GEVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDY
LQLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIADLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
NPRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARRMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRK
VVCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSPTLTLAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

ACVR2A-c046 (4I)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMPLQLLEVKARGRFGCVWKAQLLNEYVAVKIFPIQDKQSWQNEYEVYSL
PGMKHENILQFIGAEKRGTSVDVDLWLITAFHEKGSLSDFLKANVVSWNELCHIAETMARGLAYLHEDIPGLKDGH
KPAISHRDIKSKNVLLKNNLTACIADFGLALKFEAGKSAGDTHGQVGTRRYMAPEVLEGAINFQRDAFLRIDMYAM
GLVLWELASRCTAADGPVDEYMLPFEEEEIGQHPSLEDMQEVVVHKKRPPVLRDYWQKHAGMAMLCETIEECWD
HDAEARLSAGCVGERITQMQLTNI

*/ Indicates tev cleavage site.

Expression:

Cells were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using baculo infection system. Cells were transfected and after 96h harvested at 900g for 20 minutes before freezing at -20 prior to purification.

Purification:

For all samples

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate all other samples for 3 min (5 on, 10 off) on ice for baculo cells.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (approx 40ml per tube).
- Add 40ul Benzonase (1:1000 dilution) per tube to digest DNA. **DO NOT USE PEI AS IT REACTS BADLY WITH TALON RESIN.**
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 50 minutes.
- Incubate lysate with 2.5ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.
- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 2 x 25ml binding buffer (0mM imidazole, 50mM HEPES pH7.5, 500mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) and pour onto gravity flow columns.
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (10mM imidazole, 50mM HEPES pH7.5, 500mM NaCl, 5% glycerol)
- Elute in 3 x 7ml 150mM Imidazole elution buffer (50mM HEPES pH7.5, 500mM NaCl, 5% glycerol)
- Elute in 1 x 7ml 250mM Imidazole elution buffer (50mM HEPES pH7.5, 500mM NaCl, 5% glycerol)
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.
- Add Tev overnight to indicated fractions (fig 1) and incubate overnight at 4C.

Fig. 1. SDS-PAGE gel of Talon column purification for all constructs showing flowthrough, washes and elutions. Boxed fractions have Tev added and taken on to gel filtration purification.

- Concentrate down relevant fractions to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column for all samples using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 0.5mM TCEP, ph7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.

Figure 2: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1Z c108 gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a GF75 size exclusion column.

Figure 3: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1Z c113 gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a GF75 size exclusion column.

Figure 4: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR2A-c046 gel filtration samples (top) and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs (bottom) using a GF75 size exclusion column.

All Samples:

Concentrate down purified fractions until high enough concentration (>200uM if possible) in the presence of 10mM DTT. Aliquot out and flash freeze in liquid nitrogen for storage at -80C.